

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AUDU****FIRST NAME: SUNDAY****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2020 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP (samples below):

1. The basics of Essay writing (**EUCLID 2019, 1 - 4**)
2. Plagiarism (**EUCLID 2019, 5 - 13**)
3. American vs. British English (**EUCLID 2019, 27 - 35**)
4. Style guide (**EUCLID 2019, 24 - 26**)
5. Literature review (**EUCLID 2019, 17 - 23**)
6. Latin abbreviations and Expressions (**EUCLID 2020, 56 - 61**)
7. Rule of thumb for Essay writing (**EUCLID 2019, 14 - 16**)

PRINCIPLES OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have longed to develop skills in academic writing and acquire a higher degree certificate for career progression. One essential skill is the ability to communicate with other scholars the view and ideas of the writer. The ACA-401D period one study is a good starting point that challenges my rudimentary basics of English. While studying the materials, I have been able to appreciate the purpose of this study period for students to understand the course structure and learn the basic principles of academic essay writing. This study period guides the student to identify key concepts to achieve a quality essay writing and familiarization with essential tools. The course pack for the ACA-401D period one contains introductory video, Zotero training video, and books in a Portable Document Format (PDF) provided by EUCLID. The course instruction on the Learning Management System (LMS), and interestingly a cartoon that was demystifying the fear associated with academic writing, which is a common area of weakness. The principles of academic writing are essential in developing a thesis, identifying relevant materials, learning from other writers' contributions to the subject, and recognizing their effort without committing academic fraud.

2) THE FIRST CONCEPT IDENTIFIED

The first concept identified is understanding the program and course structure. The introductory video outlines the course structure mirroring the typical on-campus semester program. The course structured into seven study periods. One through five are study periods that require the student to read and interact with the course materials and write a “Response Paper” (RP) in a recommended template provided by EUCLID. A response paper should follow academic writing standards. Academic writing provides the foundation for sharing information; thus, it is the first module in the program for students to understand the basics of the subject. A response paper is not about copy and pastes from the study material which could result in plagiarism (EUCLID 2020, 3)

Period six, the student is required to develop a quiz paper while providing correct answers to the quiz and references where are found in the text or study materials provided. Period seven, the student completes a “Major Paper” (MP) as well as “viva,” which marks the end of the course. However, for ACA-401D typically has six periods. The difference between a response- and major paper; the referencing styles, wherein RP is in-text Turabian with ”List of works cited,” while MP uses the footnotes (EUCLID 2020, 2).

There are varied styles of citations which depend on the purpose of the paper and guides from the intended publisher or institution. EUCLID recommends the Turabian style. “Turabian style” is essentially the Chicago style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) (EUCLID 2019 44).

3) THE SECOND CONCEPT IDENTIFIED

The second concept identified is understanding the fundamentals of academic writing as an essential skill for postgraduate students and researchers. Academic writing is logical, factual, and information used to conclude should be verifiable. Some computer applications facilitate referencing such as “EndNote” and “Zotero,” which simplifies the tedious work of citation in academic writing.

In writing a quality essay, seven steps were identified as essential for a successful researcher to produce high-quality academic papers. These steps include; planning for the article, investigating the topic, developing a plan, writing the essay, referencing, revising, and editing the initial work, and presenting the completed work (EUCLID 2019, 1–4).

Planning for essay writing is the key to success. The EUCLID course pack states that “a good quality essay is not a sine qua non with writing down everything about the subject matter but by identifying the main thesis and responding to the questions pose” (EUCLID 2019, 1). Writing a quality essay is not a simple procedure; it is essential to develop a plan that will provide a road map as a guide.

The next essential step is to study the works of other researchers in the field. Therefore, reading is important as well as consultation with subject experts in the area of

interest. It will provide the essential guide and identification of gaps that the current work intends to address. During search and studying, it is vital to make notes and refine the identified thesis (EUCLID 2019, 2).

Academic writing is a logical process, therefore organize the points in a meaningful sequence. Start writing the initial draft. Itemizing the points provide the logical framework to produce the first copy of the main work. The introductory chapter or section and the conclusion are last to be written when one has synthesized the main points of the argument. I find this advice exciting and useful. Then revising, editing, and presenting the work with appropriate citation of the materials used to avoid plagiarism (ibid.).

4) THE THIRD CONCEPT IDENTIFIED

The third concept identified is how to avoid unacceptable behavior in academic writing, “plagiarism” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Plagiarism occurs when ideas or theories used in work without acknowledging the author or originators of such thoughts (ibid.). To avoid plagiarism is to “CITE” properly the work consulted while writing. There are two main ways of citing a material used in writing, “in-text citation and List of work cited” (EUCLID 2019, 6).

The in-text citation as the name signifies is within the body of the work identified in parenthesis using the “author-date and page number where the information is derived” (ibid.). The recommended method for response paper in EUCLID. While “List of work of cited” is another way of indicating the source of information used in an article. The recommended style for a major paper, thesis, or dissertation by EUCLID (EUCLID 2019, 10). Some software facilitates citation and formatting in academic writing. Two of these were previously unknown to me. These are “Zotero and Grammarly Editor” (EUCLID 2020, 3).

Zotero is computer software that its obtained free online. It is a referencing tool with three components for effective utilization. The Zotero application is downloaded and installed on the computer, the Zotero Chrome extension, and the Microsoft Word Plugin. When installed, the Zotero application needs to run in the background to enable the collection of materials online.

All users of Zotero to derive the full benefits of the application, need to use Chrome as their browser. The Chrome extension also referred to as “Chrome Connector,” enables an online download of books, journals, and website publications onto the computer in preferred location for ease of citation. The writer creates a folder for the project or thesis on which one is currently working in the Zotero. In the word of Cleenwerk, “Zotero is an amazing tool” (EUCLID 2017). My experience with Zotero is a must-have tool that simplifies the search, retrieval, and storage of online materials used in writing. It also enables the writer to input information on journal articles or books used in a required field on the software. It is simple to use and at no additional cost to the student.

The second tool, “Grammarly editor,” which the University provides access to, was unknown to me before starting my study at EUCLID. The Grammarly editor is another useful companion that enables writers to format their work in acceptable literal writing without ambiguity and check for plagiarism. I have identified three functions of the Grammarly editor that change my view and approach to assess scholarly articles. These are plagiarism checker, formatting tools, as well as getting tailored suggestions and alerts based on goals set by the user.

In establishing standards for generating alerts and suggestions in writing using the Grammarly editor, there are five main areas. These include; “nature of the audience, type of writing either formal or casual, domain, tone and the purpose of the article” (Grammarly Editor, 2019). The goal of the audience is to guide the writing style, and the default setting is “knowledgeable” as opposed to “general or expert.” The second goal is on the formality of the writing; it could be “informal, neutral or formal.” The third goal is the domain, which signifies whether the essay is for the “academic, business, general, casual, creative, or email.” The fourth goal is the tone of the article, with no suggested default setting. In my opinion, for academic writing, the most appropriate for the setting is “confident or analytical.” Others include; neutral, optimistic, joyful, or friendly. The other is the intent of the writing, which could be to inform, describe, convince, or tell a story. The most appropriate choice to “inform or describe” in academic essay writing

5) THE FOURTH CONCEPT IDENTIFIED

As one of the United Nations media of communication in the global community, “English” is the fourth concept identified. There are variants of “English,” the Standard British English (SBE), and Standard American English (SAE). The discussion across the globe, which one is most appropriate to use in academic writing?

“American and British English are both types of World English. Thus, they are more similar than different, especially with the educated or scientific” (EUCLID 2019, 27).

The influence of American English is evident in countries and territories colonized by the British. However, the use of “public holiday” is widespread and frequently used in Nigeria, unknown, that is American English (cf GB “bank holiday”) (EUCLID 2019, 31).

6) THE FIFTH CONCEPT IDENTIFIED

The fifth concept identified is the use of “Latin abbreviation and expression.” Latin as spoken and academic language was one of the areas of studies in medicine until recently. However, the usage of Latin in academics is still prevalent in many disciplines, such as; law, medicine, theology, et cetera. Some abbreviations and expressions in English writing are Latin without recognizing the origin. A universal language and poses threats to other languages is the ability to borrow and adapt other words in a different language. The English language has been successful over time, acquiring from other languages, including Latin.

The usage of abbreviations such as, “e.g., *exempli gratia* (for example), i.e., *id est* meaning “that is”, *et al et alia* (and others), P.M. *post meridiem* (afternoon)” are common in everyday usage without taking cognizance that the origin from Latin.

The word “viva” is regular in medical schools where the end of the rotation signals oral examination. Other popular Latin expressions include *sine qua non* (without which not, essential precondition). The Latin influenced the naming of structures in the human anatomy. For example, *triceps* (three head muscles), *biceps* (two-headed muscle), *gluteal* (buttocks), *foramina* (opening), etc. Though the Latin language is not a mandatory course in medical school is still much in usage.

7) THE SIXTH CONCEPT IDENTIFIED

Establishing standard protocols for activities ensures uniformity of results and outcomes are comparable. Therefore, students and writers need to be conversant with guidelines and styles for their work to be published. This section will focus on three related concepts in academic writing: styles guide, literature review, and a general rule of thumb for writing a quality essay.

a) Style guide for essay writing

In choosing a style of writing, which is most appropriate? There are two schools of thought; one agrees that sharing a guide minimizes ambiguity and ensures uniformity that defines a publishing company. The style guide is helpful where there are many contributing authors; the finished piece is devoid of the personal style of the writer (EUCLID 2019, 24). However, the drawback is restrictive and limits creativity. The other school of thoughts believes that a writer is at liberty to demonstrate their skills while following standard English writing style (*ibid.*).

The EUCLID 2019 coursepack concludes, “The lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means that there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on elements of style. The use of punctuation and correct grammar is well established and clear. Still, the style is much more than just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary” (*ibid.*). I did download the BBC news style guide, as recommended in the study material. The advice was explicit “the style guide is regularly updated (so do not save the attached Word document somewhere as it will quickly go out of date)” (BBC Academy).

b) Literature review

In academic writing, “*Literature review*” is essential to build on the work of other researchers. It helps the author to refine the thesis identified for discussion. There were critical elven reminders outlined in the study materials. This section discussed when to use an apostrophe before or after “s.” It reminds me of the early days where this confuses a lot.

I appreciate the guide, where possessive for “it” takes only an “s” with no apostrophe. As regards to typesetting document, the computer age has simplified the rule. Like how many spaces after a period, “the computer uses proportional fonts and justification, which create adequate white space between sentences automatically when one space typed” (EUCLID 2019, 18).

c) Rule of thumb for essay writing

Academic writing is a serious exercise, and there are common errors that can be avoided by writers following some rule of thumb. The main point of discussion should be stated, remained focused during the writing. Therefore, avoid generalities conclusion in the paper. It is essential to be explicit and specific. Other general rules introduce variation in the writing style. It is vital to avoid starting every paragraph or sentence with the same word or pattern. It makes reading boring and clumsy (EUCLID 2019, 15). Support assertion with evidence, this also help the writer to avoid plagiarism. I will discuss the rules of presenting tables and numbers in essay writing.

i) Tables

A table summarizes a large number of individuals, group of related facts which simplify understanding and compares (EUCLID 2019, 52). The guiding rules of inserting tables in work includes;

Number tables consecutively in the text, each table should be well labeled describing the contents. While adding a table, use block paragraph spacing but a single spacing within the label (heading). Rows and columns must have a title, where the content of the table is adapted from a published source is indicated. Explanatory notes are added to facilitate understanding.” The caveat is that “the more information put in a table, the difficult it is to read. Readers rarely study tables”(EUCLID 2019, 53).

A table is a useful tool for the presentation of information in a concise and easy to understand, especially in large research work.

ii) Numbers

The guiding rule in the choice between writing numbers in “word” or numerals in a body of the text is; the size of the numbers, whether it is an approximation or exact quantities of measurements (EUCLID 2019, 47). Whole numbers less than a hundred are spelled out, as well as figures at the beginning of a sentence.

In writing numbers, it is inappropriate to mix written with figures. For example, five out of a class of 45 students are girls. The acceptable way of writing could be one of the following; (5 out of a class of 45 or five out of a class of forty-five) (EUCLID 2019, 47). Similarly, numerals with a unit of measurement are spelled out, including the symbols.

8) CONCLUSION

Understanding the course structure and clear expectations from the student, I find this to be exciting. The mirroring of typical on-campus study for the online is appropriate. The course structure enables students to set goals and working with faculty staff to achieve. The course resources were adequate; for the first time, I used “Zotero and Grammarly editor.” These are amazing tools that will help me navigate the course and develop my academic writing skills.

Academic writing is essential to communicate with other scholars without ambiguity. The use of the English language, which is most appropriate, BSE, or ASE? There is no correct answer. In this study, I have learned that to be “consistent” in my writing, whichever preferred English style. Period one study has opened my eyes to the fact that I have used both America and British English in the same paper without recognizing the unacceptable error. Writing is a skill that one will develop with practice, and investment in time studying other researchers’ work is essential in writing a quality paper.

I have realized that “Latin” as language is still active in writing and communication. There are standard abbreviations and expressions that I use without recognizing the origin is Latin. The English language has been successful in borrowing and adapting words from other languages.

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